

Proton Ligand Formation Constant of *p*-(Mercaptoacetamido) Chlorobenzene (*p*-MCB) and its Formation Constants with Al(III) and Cr(III)

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The proton-ligand formation constant of *p*-(mercaptoacetamido)-chlorobenzene (*p*-MCB) and formation constants of its complexes with Al(III) and Cr(III) have been determined by Irving-Rossotti method. Refined values of Al(III), Cr(III) and also of Zn(II), VO(II), Be(II) and UO₂(II) have been obtained by Bjerrum and Schroder methods of successive approximation. The order of stability is found to be :

The metal-ligand bonding is discussed in terms of π -interaction.

IN continuation of our earlier work¹⁻⁹ this communication deals with the determination of proton-ligand formation constant of *p*-MCB and the formation constants of its complexes with Al(III) and Cr(III). Refined values of the formation constants of Zn(II), VO(II), Be(II) and UO₂(II) with *p*-MCB, are also obtained for comparison.

Experimental

The ligand, *p*-MCB, was prepared following the method described by Swain *et al.*¹⁰. All other chemicals used were of either B.D.H. Analar or equivalent quality. Since the ligand is insoluble in water, an

ethanol-water mixture (1:1 v/v) was used as solvent.

pH of the solutions was measured by using 'Polymetron CL-41 pH-meter. Reaction solutions were all thermostated at 22°±0.1°.

The experimental set up, procedure and the method of calculation are the same as described in the earlier communication.⁴

Results and Discussion

The Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹¹ was followed to

Fig. 1. Proton-ligand formation constant of *p*-MCB by linear-plot method.

Fig. 2. Formation constants of Al(III)-*p*-MCB complexes by Irving-Rossotti method.

determine the proton ligand formation constant of *p*-MCB and the formation constants of its complexes formed with aforementioned metal ions.

Mixtures consisting of the ligand, perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate were titrated with standard alkali. Similar titrations were then performed with metal salt in the reaction mixture and also without the ligand in the reaction mixture. The composition of the reaction mixtures, alkali solution and the method of calculation is the same as described earlier.⁴

Fig. 3. Formation constants of Cr(III)-*p*-MCB complexes by Irving-Rossotti method.

To calculate the formation constants of ligand-proton system, the values of $\bar{n}_A$ at different pH values were calculated using the acid and ligand titration curves, E and E+L (Figs. 2 and 3). The following formula given by Irving and Rossotti¹¹ has been used for the calculation of $\bar{n}_A$.

$$\bar{n}_A = Y + \frac{(V' - V'')(N^0 + E^0)}{(V^0 + V')TL} \quad \dots (1)$$

where V' and V'' denote the volume of alkali in acid and ligand titration curves, E and E+L, (Figs.

2 and 3), to reach the same pH value, V^0 , E^0 and N^0 are the total volume of the titration mixture, initial concentration of free acid and normality of alkali respectively.

The protonation constant of *p*-MCB has been determined by Bjerrum's half integral and also by linear plot method¹² (Fig. 1). The results are in Table 1.

The metal-ligand formation constants were obtained from the analysis of metal-ligand formation curves (Fig. 4) drawn between $\bar{n}$ and $P^{(A)}$. The values of $\bar{n}$ and $P^{(A)}$ were calculated from the equations given below :

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V''' - V'')(N^0 + E^0 + T_L(Y - \bar{n}_A))}{(V^0 + V'')\bar{n}_A T_M} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$P^{(A)} = \log_{10} \frac{1 + P_{KH} \left(\frac{1}{\text{antilog } \beta} \right)}{(T_L - T_M^0 \bar{n})} \cdot \frac{V^0 + V'''}{V^0} \quad \dots (3)$$

The values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_1^2$ for Al(III)- and Cr(III)-*p*-MCB complexes were directly read from their formation curves (Fig. 4) and are recorded in Table 1. The corresponding values for Zn(II), VO(II), Be(II) and UO₂(II) complexes reported by us⁵ in the earlier communication are also recorded in Table 1 for comparison. The refined values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ obtained in the present study, employing Bjerrum's method of successive approximation¹³ and by convergence formula of Schroden for successive approximation¹⁴ are also given in Table 1.

The values recorded in Table 1 indicate that the stability ($\log K_1$) follows the order :

This order of stability follows neither the Irving-Williams rule¹⁵ nor any of the empirical orders reviewed by them. The complete disagreement of the Irving-Williams order in the present case may be attributed to the π -interaction in M-S bond.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF SOME *p*-MCB COMPLEXES

Method Complex	Irving-Rossotti			Bjerrum Successive Approximation			Schroden		
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K\beta_2$
Al(III)- <i>p</i> -MCB	7.61	6.90	14.51	7.55	6.95	14.50	7.60	6.90	14.50
Cr(III)- <i>p</i> -MCB	7.38	5.63	13.01	7.42	5.60	13.02	7.35	5.65	13.00
Zn(II)- <i>p</i> -MCB	7.14	6.60	13.74	7.14	6.55	13.69	7.10	6.60	13.70
VO(II)- <i>p</i> -MCB	7.07	6.53	13.60	6.96	6.60	13.56	7.00	6.55	13.55
Be(II)- <i>p</i> -MCB	6.35	5.46	11.81	6.30	5.46	11.76	6.35	5.40	11.75
UO ₂ (II)- <i>p</i> -MCB	5.87	5.24	11.11	5.82	5.25	11.07	5.85	5.20	11.05
<i>p</i> -MCB	9.02	—	—	9.05*	—	—			

* Linear plot method, (Fig. 1).

Standard deviations by least square method, $\log K_1 \pm 0.03$, $\log K_2 \pm 0.05$, $\log \beta_2 \pm 0.10$.

It is observed that all these complexes are quite stable indicating the possibility of M-S π -interaction contributing to the stability. The possibility of π -interaction in the M-S bond in the transition metal complexes have been indicated in the literature¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Fig. 4. Formation curves for p -MOB complexes of Al(III) and Cr(III).

However, Al(III) and Be(II) being non-transition metals do not have π -electrons to donate to d -orbitals of sulphur atom of p -MCB and hence no M-S π -interaction can take place. This accounts for the class A character of the Al(III) and Be(II) ions^{19,20}. VO(II) is a transition metal ion but tetravalent vanadium has only one d π -electron and hence M-S π -interaction is not very effective. In case of Cr(III), although it is a transition metal ion, has only three d π -electrons and three positive charges and hence M-S π -interaction will not be high²¹. Because of trivalent state O $\rightarrow$ M σ -interaction is more. Thus M-O $>$ M-S and accounts for Class A character of the Cr(III) ion¹⁹, UO₂(II) has no α -electrons available for back bonding and hence the bond is only σ in character. The higher stability of Zn(II) complex

may be attributed to greater M-L π -interaction between the π -orbitals of Zn(II) and the ligand. Complexes of Al(III) are generally found to be less stable than those of Cr(III) but in certain instances Al(III) is reported to form stronger complexes than Cr(III)², an observation in agreement with our findings.

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